

THERMAL ACCELERATED AGING STUDY OF BINDERS FOR PROPELLANT APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Propellants in launch vehicles and missiles generate the thrust required to reach a destination or target. While propellants for launch vehicles can be prepared a few months or post-curing before launch, this is not the case for military applications. Typically, for such applications, propellants are stored for a longer time period, with a shelf life ranging from 10 to 15 years. Any material exposed to environmental conditions deteriorates with storage and causes variation in both mechanical and chemical properties. Propellants are not an exception to such degradation. Once degradation reaches a threshold limit, it can impact the performance, thereby resulting in mission failures.

The ageing of composite solid propellants is a critical topic as it influences the rocket performance and failure parameters in response to storage time. This research project investigates the impact of cyclic temperature variation as a natural stimulant on Hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene, which is a binder in the standard composite propellant composition in formulation with ammonium perchlorate. Many literature has studied the ballistic and mechanical properties variation of aged propellants in accelerated isothermal conditions. However, only a few have discussed the impact of the natural sinusoidal nature of temperature distribution.

This work focuses on determining the temperature amplitude accounting for both high frequency diurnal and low frequency seasonal temperature variations over a ten years period in Jaisalmer, bringing the climate chamber into operation, determining the activation energies and mechanical properties of unaged two grade of cured HTPB. Seasonal temperature amplitudes were obtained by taking mean of collected data for ten years. The activation energies for both HTPB variant is found to be almost similar to that of presented in the literature. The crosslink density for aged sample nearly doubled compared to that of the unaged samples, determined using equilibrium swelling method. The elongation percentage decreased by approximately 40%, modulus increased to more than twice that of the unaged specimen, and tensile strength exhibited an increase of nearly 47% relative to the original unaged value.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
DOA	Di-octyl Adipate
E_a	Activation Energy
H12MDI	Desmodur-W
HDI	1,6-Hexamethylene diisocyanate
HMX	Cyclotetramethylene tetranitramine
HTPB	Hydroxyl Terminated Polybutadiene
IPDI	Isophorone diisocyanate
NC	Nitrocellulose
NG	Nitroglycerine
RDX	Cyclotrimethylene trinitramine
TDI	Toulene diisocyanate
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
THF	Tetrahydrofuran
UTM	Universal Testing Machine

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 SOLID ROCKET PROPELLANTS

Solid propellants play a significant role in both launch vehicles and defense systems, with each system tailoring the propellant characteristics to meet mission requirements. The higher density impulse and thrust profile make solid motors the sole preferred choice in booster stages. These are classified based on multiple performance criteria such as burn rate, thrust generation, and specific impulse, while satisfying the structural factor of safety constraints. In rocket applications, these propellants are expected to deliver the adiabatic flame temperature as high as 3600 K. The solid propellants which typically constitute 87% of the total mass of solid rocket engines are stored within the combustion chamber in specific grain geometries as demanded by the mission profile to optimize burn characteristics and enhance performance^[1]. Upon ignition, the burnt surface generates high temperature gases that increase the chamber pressure required to achieve the desired thrust. Solid propellants are broadly classified into two categories based on their microstructural composition:

1.1.1 HOMOGENEOUS PROPELLANTS

In homogeneous propellants, the constituents are mixed at the molecular level. Nitrocellulose (NC), fuel in solid form, and Nitroglycerine (NG), oxidizer in liquid form, are the major ingredients of the homogeneous solid propellant. NC consists of a linear chain of carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen atoms, along with a radical of nitrogen, the concentration of which depends on the degree of nitration. Presence of both the fuel and oxidizer within each molecule can make individual NC or NG as propellants and thus are called monopropellants. NG is inherently oxygen-rich, whereas NC is fuel-rich with an oxygen deficiency of approximately 30%^[2]. The combustion of these propellants produces minimal smoke, making them highly suitable for defense applications. Depending on the operational needs, plasticizers and stabilizers are incorporated in certain concentrations to enhance their tolerance range to mechanical impact and environmental stress. Ho-

homogeneous propellants have their usability based on the mission application. They are further classified based on their formulation into a) Single base b) Double base and c) Triple base propellants

1.1.2 COMPOSITE PROPELLANTS

Also called as heterogeneous propellant due to composition of highly particle-filled polymer binder matrix and compounds/elements, composite propellants consist of solid oxidizers and liquid fuels/binders that bind together all the compounds. Unlike homogeneous propellants, the individual oxidizers and fuel can be identified in this propellant as they do not undergo molecular mixing and remain physically distinguishable within the matrix. Extensive research has concluded the use of ammonium perchlorate and hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene (HTPB) as the best oxidizer and fuel respectively for composite solid propellants. Nonetheless, some research studies on improving the energy output has indicated the possibility of using nitramines such as RDX and HMX as potential high energy ingredients^[3]. The superior chemical compatibility of HMX with other additives makes it a more practical choice than RDX while considering safe practices in dealing with such energetic compounds.

1.2 POLYMERIC FUELS

The mixture of oxidizer and fuel in solid propellant requires the use of a liquid-phase polymer binder. Among multiple options as polymeric binder, liquid prepolymers like HTPB are widely employed because of their favorable mechanical properties and compatibility with energetic components. The addition of diisocyanates initiates a polymerization reaction of the chain leading to solidification through cross-linking, and binding of the oxidizers and metallic powder post-successful curing. For formulation with solid loading range of 84–88%, remaining 12–16% by weight is the liquid binder^[2]. Due to their viscoelastic nature, in mixture with binders like HTPB, the propellant is susceptible to deformation due to slumping that varies as a function of time^[4]. Therefore, it should be capable of withstanding higher thermal and mechanical stress under both storage and operational conditions. Binders can either be thermoplastic or thermosetting. The typical binder properties are provided in the table below.

1.3 HTPB - EPOXY BLENDS

An alternative strategy to address long term property degradation with time is modifying the binder composition that undergo transformation in chemical structure and exhibit superiority than the existing composition. Formulation of HTPB-epoxy blends is a promising approach that combine the energetic characteristic of HTPB with robustness of epoxy resins. Epoxies are known for their high adhesive strength, non-hygroscopic

Table 1.1: Ideal binder properties

Properties	Value
Molecular weight, g/mol	2500–5000
Viscosity, Pa.s	1–10
Minimum density, kg/m ³	800–1000
Glass transition temperature, °C	80 to -60
Functionality	> 2
Poly-dispersity	> 1 & < 2

nature, and low shrinkage properties. As they contain multiple epoxide groups for each molecule and has three-dimensional cross-linked structures^[5], substituting these improve the durability and resilience of HTPB-based binders.

LY 556, a pale yellow liquid Bisphenol-A epichlorohydrin based epoxy resin, has low tendency to crystallize^[6] and has long pot life as a reactive diluent free matrix system. Upon curing, it exhibits very good high temperature performance, offering good mechanical and thermal properties^[7]. Epoxy CY 230 -1, a cycloaliphatic based epoxy resin^[8] demonstrate strong resistance to atmospheric and chemical degradation. During curing, the hydroxyl groups of HTPB undergo nucleophilic addition reaction with electrophilic carbonyl groups of LY 556 and CY 230-1^[8]. The reaction causes opening of epoxide rings leading to the formation of covalent ether bond between HTPB and epoxies. Introducing these additives causes viscosity variation and crosslink integrity impacting the miscibility and processing behaviour in preparing propellants which are discussed in detail in the results section.

Table 1.2: Physical properties of Epoxies

Properties	CY 230-1	LY 556
Viscosity, Pa.s	1.35 - 2	10 - 12
Density, kg/m ³	1100 - 1200	1150 - 1200
Epoxide index, Eq/kg	4.2 - 4.35	5.30 - 5.45
Flash point, °C	160	> 200

1.4 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND AGEING

Solid propellants in storage undergo changes in their mechanical properties over time. The degradation of these properties of the propellant over time is primarily attributed to forces and stresses including static loading^[9]. A dominant phenomenon in this context is creep, where under constant propellant load induces deformation over an extended period compromising its structural integrity. This deformation leads to physical distortion such as strain, and elongation or shrinkage of the propellant that has a direct correlation to the performance parameters. Beside static loading, other factors responsible for age-

ing include environmental exposure such as high-temperature fluctuations that introduce thermal stresses that can result in the development of cracks and delamination, fatigue due to repeated loading and unloading cycles reducing the overall strength of the material and driving to failure during operations. The changes in mechanical properties is the function of propellant dimension and grain geometry that further influence the ageing behavior. All these factors in combination determine the mechanical aging of the propellant.

Figure 1.1: Mechanical Deformation

Aged propellants depict correlations between universal compression strength, tensile strength, and inherent viscosity conditions^[10]. This study contributes to the investigation of potential links between burn rate variation and changes in the mechanical properties. As ageing progresses, the transition in properties due to gradual decomposition takes place altering the mechanical properties that were in unaged state. The gradual decomposition of the propellant, in formulations with larger concentrations of ammonium perchlorate, accounts for the mechanical degradation. This high chemical reactivity property of AP oxidizers introduces complex ageing dynamics that affect the overall stability of the propellant matrix.

Propellants with higher solid loading generally tend to show an increased tendency towards higher ballistic properties such as in burn rate^[11]. However, this comes at the cost of reduced ultimate tensile strength and lower compression strength^[10]. Therefore, there should always be a choice for the balance range of acceptable criteria while considering both the mechanical integrity and ballistic efficiency. The mechanical properties of aged propellants have been found to decrease in relation to the storage time. Irrespective of the various solid particles in the composition, propellants fail due to dewetting of binder to filler bonds, acting as an early indicator to motor failure and leading to tears in the propellant structure^[12]. However, the use of different particle sizes and their distribution can have a significant impact on the mechanical properties of cured propellant^[13]. Thus,

an increased proportion of fine AP particles causes reduced elongation while increasing the propellant strength^[14,15]. The authors also verified the importance of using bimodal distribution in order to exhibit higher propellant strength and increased ductility.

The binder chemical structure itself impacts the mechanical properties which are heavily influenced by the percentage of curing agent used for the propellant formation. The standard use of diisocyanates makes it relevant to form a urethane linkage, thereby, the higher the percentage of diisocyanates such as TDI, and IPDI, the higher the strength. Thus, curing agents have a huge impact on the mechanical performance which can play a pivotal role during storage of the propellant. In some practices, chain extenders are also used that increase the molecular weight to enhance mechanical properties. Diols such as 1,4- butanediol (BDO) and 1,4,-cyclohexane dimethanol, HTPB and diisocyanates i.e. Desmodur-W(H12MDI), IPDI, and 1,6-Hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) have been explored in works of literature. The tensile strength increased when HTPB – H12MDI is used with BDO as depicted in the picture below^[16]. From this study in the literature, an increase in tensile strength stagnates increasing the percentage composition of diols and diisocyanate up to 2 mol of diols per mole of HTPB, after which it reached yield point.

Figure 1.2: Tensile Strength vs diols for different compositions

[16]

Thus, it can be conferred that the elongation and tensile properties vary with the changes in composition. The natural stimulant is expected to influence these properties throughout time, thereby, leading to the ageing of propellants and mechanical degradation based on compositions.

Oxidative degradation results in a reduced sol content, which in turn increases the crosslinking of the binder-propellant mixture. Crosslink density is one of the most suitable ageing evaluation parameter that influences the mechanical properties such as tensile strength, modulus, swelling, and glass transition temperature^[17]. Generally, Flory-

Rehner equation is adapted to find the crosslink density via equilibrium swelling method. However, there are several models available to find the crosslink density.

According to Charlesby-Pinner equation^[18],

$$S + \sqrt{S} = \frac{p_0}{q_0} + \frac{1}{q_0 P_n D} \quad (1.1)$$

where S is the sol fraction. P_n is the number averaged degree of polymerization and D is the radiation dose, p_0 is density of fracture per unit dose and q_0 is density of crosslinking per unit dose.

This equation is dependent on 'S' which represents the sol content, defined as the fraction of the binder extractable using solvents. Upon oxidative cross-linking due to exposure to atmospheric air, the sol content of binder reduces, increasing the relative cross-link density. This, in turn, increases the stiffness of the propellant. The trend comes in agreement with the experimental data as illustrated in figure 1.4a and 1.4b^[19]. Therefore, unaged samples are expected to have lower crosslink density as compared to the aged samples. Chemical crosslinks, permanently trapped (non-sliding) chain entanglements and temporarily trapped (sliding type) chain entanglements are three types of crosslinks that dominate throughout the ageing of propellants and binders beside plasticizer migration. Because of the role of individual or either in combination of these types of crosslinks in a material, crosslink density calculated based on different model varies.

Figure 1.3: Types of molecular crosslinking and chain entanglements

(a) Stress at different temperature

(b) Strain at different temperature

Figure 1.4: Stress and Strain plot as a function of storage time

The key parameter, relaxation modulus is sensitive to crosslinking during ageing, for which the stress relaxation test is one of the best methods to determine the mechanical properties of strain aged sample^[20]. For PBAN propellant, strain during ageing does not alter the rate of change of chemical reactions, however, it has side effects on mechanical properties. Samples strained till 12% depicted reduced relaxation modulus, but stress and strain remained the same as unstrained samples^[20]. Crosslinking of chemical AP and polymeric binder causes alterations in the compound structure that raise the propellant stiffness^[21].

With oxidizer loading, the burn rate for unaged propellants increases. The higher oxidizer loading causes an increase in the chemical reactivity of the propellant which typically increases the burn rate of unaged propellant. One might expect propellant to degrade massively with ageing because of this more reactivity, but the research suggests otherwise, that with ageing, the degradation is lower for higher solid loading^[22]. Even though the degradation is lower with higher solid loading that may improve the ballistic properties, it concurrently decreases mechanical and rheological properties^[11]. This demands executing the appropriate proportionate propellant formulation highlighting the requirement of trade-off to maintain balance.

The reaction of isocyanate with the hydroxyl groups of HTPB, a soft segment of polyurethane, reduces surface energy and yields higher viscoelastic properties; however, these properties undergo significant degradation upon exposure to air^[23]. Dynamic characterisation of propellants is prominent in literature for its unique advantage in studying viscoelastic properties. It is a thermo-mechanical analysis technique that assists in studying the viscoelastic behaviour of a material by applying oscillatory loading. In DMA, cyclic deformation is applied, and the mechanical properties are recorded. Storage modulus, a material's ability to store elastic energy^[24], loss modulus, a modulus that represents how much energy is lost while restoring the energy^[25], which is related to

the viscous dissipation, and loss tangent also called damping efficiency, a ratio of loss modulus to the storage modulus, are the primary outcome of this test. The run for both unaged and aged can be performed which can be plotted to show the variation in these properties.

The mechanical properties depends on multiple parameters such as hydroxyl groups, density, molecular weight and microstructure of HTPB as depicted in the literature^[26]. Shaghayeghi Toosi *et al.* (2014) used three types of HTPB having viscosity in the range of 6750 to 7120 cPa, constant density of 870 kg/m³ and of different molecular weight. The storage modulus for these HTPB variants cured with TDI are shown in the figure 1.5. Before glass transition region, there is a difference of almost 1.5×10^8 Pa, after which there is not significance differences in the modulus till around -25°C .

Figure 1.5: Storage modulus vs Temperature for different HTPB variants

1.5 CHEMICAL PROPERTIES AND AGEING

While most of the inferred idea is that oxidative degradation happens when propellants are exposed to ambient conditions based on the observation on polystyrene and ammonium perchlorate by one of the papers, atmospheric air has negligible impact on the formation of peroxide^[10]. The peroxide formation takes place largely due to polystyrene and ammonium perchlorate interaction where AP undergoes thermal decomposition, which decreases with increasing loading^[27]. The experimental verification depicted the rate change in burn rate and thermal decomposition rate as almost similar. This presents the contradicting view on the matter when the comparison is done against the conclusion of another paper that binder materials undergo oxidative crosslinking in the presence of air^[28] serving to be the most dominant degradation mechanism^[19]. The propellant is confirmed to be aged due to thermal decomposition of the ammonium perchlorate irrespective of its combination with other materials which was verified after receiving the activation energy same for both the combined PS/AP and AP alone. However such de-

composition would be lower for the composition with higher solid loading. As a result, the burn rate is not affected much.

Figure 1.6: Burn rate of propellant with different loadings [14]

Ageing samples exhibit changes in the texture with redistribution of particles. Though the solid phase reaction rate of oxidizer and crosslinking of the binder is relatively unaffected by environmental temperature fluctuations, the reaction in the solution phase is much affected bringing fluctuation in nucleation frequency^[29]. The temperature difference excites the reaction mechanism in the propellant composition which leads to varying nucleation frequency. The dynamic interplay between various chemical processes determines the particle distribution essential for predicting the evolution of propellant properties.

Plasticizer migration happens with time due to the nature of flow from a higher concentration region to a lower concentration region. Usually, the migration takes place from the inner region to the surface level of the motor, degrading the mechanical integrity. One way to prevent migration is to perform continuous experiments with all the plasticizers available. It is observed that samples prepared with a meagre ratio of energetic materials, also known as low-vulnerability-ammunition samples, had very low evaporative loss due to which plasticizer migration from the inner zone to the outer surface of the propellant is prevented^{[30][31][32]}. Not limited to this, if the propellant motor is stored in a confined environment, plasticizer loss can be minimized significantly^[19].

Figure 1.7: Storage time vs weight loss of Plasticizers [33]

The choice among multiple plasticizers can alter the ageing phenomenon by a noticeable amount. The experiment on the choice of plasticizers and their response after ageing at a particular temperature has usually found that Diphenylamine lies as the least favourable with Methylidiphenylurea as the best one [33].

The migration behaviour of NG content too depicts a similar trend as plasticiser. At high temperatures, the NG migration increases in a significant amount such that the propellant ages quickly [34].

Figure 1.8: Storage time vs NG content in Boundary Layer [34]

The safe shelf life for the storage of propellant should consider multifaceted properties. One of such properties is to determine the products formed due to reactions that occur throughout ageing. This is accompanied by a change in the chemical composition. For example, for a fixed oxidizer and fuel, the use of different plasticizers or stabilizers helps determine stable products formed during the ageing period. The higher the number of stabilizer reaction products, the more degraded the propellant is [33].

Literature has been emphasizing that the thermal degradation of AP has direct relations to Arrhenius equation. However, one study suggested that AP degradation is slower at low activation energy and higher at higher activation energy in the presence of Nickel chromium catalyst^[35]. It is stated that the collision frequency factor goes up for the catalyzed decomposition. This suggests that the behaviour of the propellant could be affected based on catalyzed and uncatalyzed decomposition. In turn, the ageing characteristics of propellant are thus impacted based on the composition.

1.6 MOTIVATION

With the evolution of rocket flights, the demand for enhanced safety and stability for efficient performance has substantially increased. Any changes in the solid propellant structure and chemical composition during storage are undesirable as it could lead to the propellant failure. Both diurnal and seasonal temperature variation acts as the environmental stimulants that accelerate degradation mechanisms. One such phenomenon is creep that primarily dominates the structural integrity of the propellant, where a constant load causes deformation over an extended period. This manifests to physical distortions such as strain and elongation, or shrinkage of the propellant, which has a direct correlation to the performance parameters. Studying such variation in properties provides valuable insights to improve not only the propellant shelf life but also to expand its utility in many other polymeric applications.

Isothermal studies considers the homogeneous distribution of temperature within the motor. This avoids the impact of daily and seasonal temperature variations using a constant mean temperature profile throughout the accelerated process. However, in actual scenarios, the temperature varies across grains, making the temperature heterogeneously distributed. Thus, this spatial temperature fluctuation causes uneven heat transfer in the propellant, leading to more degradation on the outer surface of the grain while on the inner side, the thermal stimulus is less pronounced. This creates performance imbalance and the motor is subjected to potential structural vulnerability. Thus, this project aims to bridge the research gap by evaluating the impact of accelerated temperature profile accounting for diurnal and season based calculations instead of diurnal and year-based, with the goal of finding compositions effective to enhance existing properties over time.

1.7 OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this project is to study the ageing of binders and composite solid propellants prioritizing the impact of daily and seasonal temperature variation on propellant properties. Thus, it primarily focuses on changes in mechanical properties of binders and composite solid propellants, elucidating the intricate relation between the propellant composition and environmental conditions.

Furthermore, studying naturally aged samples will consume the equivalent natural time. However, by accelerating the degradation process while ensuring that the changes in properties are natural, the ageing time is reduced significantly. In many studies, isothermal ageing in climate chambers has been adopted^[11,19,20,29,36]. However, stored propellants are constantly exposed to daily and seasonal temperature fluctuations, making the results obtained from isothermal not truly resonate with actual conditions^[9,37,38]. Hence, my work aims to study the exact variation in properties after ageing for binders and propellants and find out solutions to slow degradation mechanisms before determining the safe storage limit.

The major objectives of this project include finding the activation energies using thermogravimetric analysis taking references from seasonal meteorological temperature profiles recorded for ten years in Jaisalmer. Another key objective is to calculate the accelerated ageing time while satisfying the criteria for time required to reach homogeneous temperature distribution. Laboratory-based experiments such as dynamic mechanical analysis, tensile testing, and cross-linking density will be carried out that confirms to the degradation in aged specimen. Afterwards, I plan to prepare HTPB–epoxy blends that could enhance the required properties followed by the ageing of propellant samples.

The binder and propellant samples will be kept in the climate chamber with increased stimulant, the mechanical and ballistic properties of which will be calculated after completing the accelerated cycle.

1.8 THESIS ORGANIZATION

This thesis is structured into four chapters, including the present chapter. The information about the study, including the background and a detailed review of literature are discussed in the Chapter 1. Particular emphasis is placed on the impact of ageing on the mechanical and chemical properties of the binder and propellants. Chapter 2 describes the experimental methodology. It outlines steps followed for collecting temperature data from reliable meteorological sources, preparing test specimens, applying Arrhenius equation and utilizing instruments to perform necessary calculations in order to determine performance parameters. The Chapter 3, results and discussion, presents about changes in specimen properties such as crosslink density, storage modulus and elongation percentage as a function of aging. Finally, Chapter 4 concludes the study with summary about key findings, conclusions, and emphasizing the future research directions aimed at improving the shelf life of propellants.

Chapter 2

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The effect of ageing on binder properties was investigated through a series of mechanical tests. The behaviour of aged binder samples will be compared with the unaged binder mechanical properties to study the extent of degradation. The variation in these properties will be numerically analyzed to extract relevant information about the influence of stimulants. Similarly, tensile tests on aged binders will be conducted, the outcome of which will be compared with the unaged binder to evaluate changes. The overall methodology followed in this project is illustrated in the flowchart below which follows sequential steps from ambient temperature analysis and pre-ageing characterization for the binder to post-ageing evaluation and comparison.

To fulfill all objectives as stated, the following activities have been performed.

- Initiate the ageing chamber setup after procuring essential components such as thermocouples and the RS485 communication module, enabling a smooth transition from manual-based operation to system-based control.
- Conduct a literature review and perform numerical analysis using Python to calculate the accelerated ageing time for each season.
- Prepare liquid silicone rubber-based mould for sample fabrication using laser-cut acrylic shapes.

Figure 2.1: Research Methodology

2.1 AMBIENT TEMPERATURE DATA PROCESSING

The temperature data of Jaisalmer for the past 11 years (2013 to 2023) was collected from two sites: (www.wunderground.com) and (meteostat.net). Due to the unavailability of hourly temperature data for the whole 10 years at one site, and with only 8 recorded temperatures per day, the other site was sought for data reliability.

The temperature data for a year are divided into three seasons: winter, from November to February; summer, from March to June; and monsoon, from July to October, as per the literature^[39]. Afterwards, the mean for each hour in a day for a particular season is calculated in Excel. The calculated mean for each season from 2013 to 2022 is then averaged to get one characteristic profile for a season. Finally, three averaged characteristic profiles are achieved season-wise as shown in the figure 2.2a,2.2b,2.2c and the plot for the three mean characteristic profile is plotted as shown in 2.3.

Figure 2.2: Comparison of season-based temperature from 2014-2022

Figure 2.3: Characteristic temperature profile for three seasons

2.1.1 SEASON-BASED TEMPERATURE AMPLITUDE

The amplitude on a particular day is determined by taking half of the difference between the maximum and minimum temperatures. The average amplitude temperature distribution with a maximum number of occurrences is considered for the amplitude. For winter, as shown in 2.4c, 82 out of 121 days have an amplitude in the range of 6 to 7°C, the average of which gives 6.5°C as the temperature amplitude. Likewise, it is 6.5°C and 4.75°C for summer and monsoon, respectively.

Figure 2.4: Season-based amplitude histogram, Jaisalmer

Table 2.1: Diurnal Temperature Variations by Season

Season	Seasonal Data	Diurnal Mean	Diurnal Amplitude	Diurnal Highest	Diurnal Lowest
Winter	Min	17.84	5.52	23.96	12.79
	Max	20.48	6.71	27.27	14.55
	Avg.	19.17	6.24	25.93	13.44
Summer	Min	30.61	5.82	37.11	24.92
	Max	33.22	6.96	40.14	26.65
	Avg.	32.02	6.22	38.19	25.74
Monsoon	Min	29.84	4.46	34.65	25.53
	Max	31.46	5.28	36.79	26.91
	Avg.	30.91	4.98	36.24	26.27

2.1.2 SINUSOIDAL TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION

Several empirical models are discussed in the literature to accurately build the mathematical relation for the temperature distribution throughout the day. Some models include day partition into the three segments: time from sunrise to the time when the temperature for a day reaches maximum, maximum temperature time to the time during sunset, and sunset to the next sunrise^[40]. In comparison, the other includes only two segments: the time from minimum temperature to sunset, and from sunset to the next day's minimum temperature. One research study found that the sine exponential model gives the lowest mean square error that best estimates the temperature fluctuation than the simple sinusoidal model^[41]. However, the authors found that the narrower time gap temperature data improved the accuracy of all the models.

Similarly, another study concluded that the higher accuracy rate of the sinusoidal model is suitable for the clear climatic condition^[42] that can be applied for the selected location, Jaisalmer, in the project. A similar model is used in the cyclic accelerated ageing study by Hamza et al. Thus, this sinusoidal temperature distribution equation is utilised for this research work as in the literature^[37].

For the cycle of natural ageing stimulants,

$$T_n(t) = T_m + T_d \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_n} + \phi\right) \quad (2.1)$$

where T_m is the mean temperature for a day, T_d is the temperature amplitude that remains constant for a season. τ_n is 24 hours, and ϕ is the phase shift that represents the peak,

which is shifted to the right in this case.

$$\phi = -\frac{2\pi t_{\max}}{\tau} \quad (2.2)$$

Here, t_{\max} is the hour the temperature reaches peak for a day, and τ is either τ_n or τ_a for use in the respective equation.

For the cycle of accelerated ageing stimulants, the mean temperature is increased without altering the other parameters. This additional mean temperature provides the freedom to choose the value such that the maximum accelerated temperature does not exceed 65°C ensuring the natural degradation remains dominant throughout the study^[37].

$$T_a(t) = T_m + \Delta T_m + T_d \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau_a} + \phi\right) \quad (2.3)$$

For the propellant and binder that undergo degradation, the reaction rate is

$$R = k[B_i]^{n_i} \quad (2.4)$$

And the rate constant, which is proportional to the exponent of activation energy, is given as

$$k = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_n(t)}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

The change in progress of the reaction relation with the Arrhenius equation^[37] is

$$\frac{dP}{dt} \propto A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_n(t)}\right) \quad (2.6)$$

To have a similar degradation for both cyclic and natural ageing, the activation energy should be the same^[37]. For similar activation energy, the degradation rate constant is equal for both the natural and accelerated profiles. The solution of this equation gives the accelerated time for a day.

$$\sum_{N=1}^{365} \int_0^{\tau_n} A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_n(t)}\right) dt = \sum_{N=1}^{365} \int_0^{\tau_a} A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_a(t)}\right) dt \quad (2.7)$$

The above equation involves a temperature- and time-dependent function in exponential form, making it difficult to solve using an analytical approach. Thus, numerical integration with the grid search method in Python programming was applied to calculate the accelerated time.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP: AGEING CHAMBER

The ageing chamber was brought into full working condition from scratch to enable the accelerated cyclic thermal ageing study. To ensure the temperature profile can reach the required thermal conditions, the maximum operable temperature was set above 80°C using adjuster located at the rearside of the incubator. During operational condition, there was water leakage from the system resulting from the failure of solenoid valve that led to improper actuation. It was subsequently repaired to ensure no leakages through the system. Initially, five T-type thermocouples were installed on each tray to assess temperature distribution across the vertical sections of the chamber. The uniformity of the distribution was validated reading temperature distribution across inner wall of the chamber. Water circulation to maintain thermal regulation was maintained through a designated water pipeline.

Communication between the control software and the incubator was established in stepwise configuration. An iTools Engineering Studio Manager interface in the system communicates to the incubator through RS485-to-USB converter as incubator has built-in RS485 serial communication bus, allowing digital interfacing. The temperature variation across the chamber is controlled by Proportional–Integral–Derivative Controller, namely Eurotherm 2404 model. Prior to initiating the final thermal cycle, the test run were conducted multiple times to ensure smooth and stable temperature profile minimizing the difference between setup value and the created value.

(a) Climate Chamber for accelerated ageing study

(b) 15 T-type thermocouples to monitor temperature throughout the sample compartment

Figure 2.5: Ageing experimental setup

Figure 2.6: Temperature monitoring setup with system–chamber integration

2.2.1 ISOTHERMAL ACCELERATED AGEING

Following the step by step approach, initially, the chamber was run through isothermal conditions, as it was the easiest way to operate. The acceptable temperature deviation was set at 2°C , which means even if set temperature is 41°C , the program starts running from 39°C to 43°C . This temperature deviation is selected based on multiple test runs where temperature did not exceed beyond 2°C difference. The maximum variation from the set value in the plot below is observed around 0.8°C , which is within the acceptable range.

Figure 2.7: Isothermal temperature profile at 40°C for 24 hours

2.2.2 CYCLIC THERMAL ACCELERATED AGEING

The initial run required a longer operating time to transition from the ramp to run condition in the chamber. Nevertheless, it was understood that for the chamber to operate efficiently across multiple cycles, the transition in cycle should not follow an abrupt drop or rise from the final point in order for other cycle to run smoothly without delay. Figures 2.8a and 2.8b represent a relatively smooth transition between cycles throughout the chamber operation. The profile in figure 2.8 consists of seven temperature segments with run time for each segment of 15 minutes summing up to a total of 105 minutes. However, the internal adjustment of the system extended the cycle time to approximately 120 minutes. Same is the case in figure 2.9 where the expected duration of 240 minutes exceeded due to system regulation.

After multiple iteration, the gap between estimated time and actual time is reduced configuring the compressor time for both RAMP and RUN condition so that workload for the Proportional-Integral-Derivative Controller is reduced. The accelerated temperature profile is then developed with the calculation of accelerated ageing time as shown in the figure 3.8. The variation in calculated and actual accelerated time is reflected in the table 3.5.

(a) Thermocouple readings

(b) Present Value and Set Point - iTools

Figure 2.8: Program 9 Temperature readings in Climate Chamber

(a) Thermocouple readings

(b) Present Value and Set Point - iTools

Figure 2.9: Program 10 Temperature readings in Climate Chamber

The actual temperature profile found from the sinusoidal equation was run in the incubator. The reason behind

Figure 2.10: Actual temperature profile across three seasons

2.3 ASTM STANDARD SPECIMEN PREPARATION & GEOMETRY

Initially, the acrylic sheet is cut into multiple ASTM D638 Type IV standard shapes using a 130 W CO₂ CNC Laser Cutter. The liquid silicone rubber elastomers are used in equal proportion and mixed. The ASTM acrylic shapes are placed into the mould frame and sprayed with a mould releasing agent. The silicone elastomer without bubbles is poured into the tray where the mould is left for curing for 24 hours, and it is ready to be used for sample preparations.

The polymer matrix, HTPB and plasticiser, DOA is added to the beaker, which is thoroughly mixed for approximately 15 minutes at room temperature. The mixture is left at 65 °C in a hot air oven for approximately 30 minutes. It is then blended with the addition of a curing agent TDI and kept in the oven for 20 minutes at 65 °C. The mixture is deaerated using a desiccator with a motor power capacity of 200 W. The final solution is cast into the silicone moulds. Special care is needed while pouring the blend into the mould as gap between the mould and pouring beaker causes bubble formation. The binder specimen of 4mm thickness is cured at 60°C for 6 days. The dimension for the non-rigid plastic was selected as per ASTM standard D638 Type IV^[43].

Similarly, HTPB–blends with epoxies were prepared. The total composition for the samples are given in the table.

Table 2.2: Blend Compositions

Sample Code	HTPB	LY 556	CY 230	DOA	TDI
S1	80	-	-	14.8	5.2
S2	70	-	10	14.8	5.2
S3	70	10	-	14.8	5.2

(a) ASTM D638 Type IV

(b) Sample Preparation

Figure 2.11: Dimension for D638 Type IV specimen

Figure 2.12: Schematic of ASTM standard sample preparation

2.4 HEAT TRANSFER ACROSS A HTPB SLAB

12 T-type thermocouples were kept at the mid-section of the cured HTPB slab of the dimension 238mm * 142mm * 4mm. The distance between thermocouples are maintained constant in both vertical and horizontal direction. The diameter of thermocouples bead is 1.8 mm and the hole drilled to the half distance is 0.9 mm. To ensure there is no heat loss from the thermocouple inserted surface and avoid falling of thermocouples, epoxy resin was used to hold.

Figure 2.13: Thermocouples embedded at the mid-thickness of the HTPB slab

2.5 INSTRUMENTATION & ANALYSIS

2.5.1 THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

Thermogravimetric Analysis, or TGA, is an analytical technique that measures the mass variation concerning temperature when certain heating rates are applied. The main objective of this analysis is to find the material's thermal stability and decomposition behaviour. The decomposition data for temperature can be utilised to generate the weight loss plots that help to identify the steps involved in decomposition, oxidation, and evaporation^[44]. The data can further be utilized to find out the activation energy of each stage using the different models available. This kinetic analysis helps in getting information about the impact the process parameters can have on feedstock conversion^[45].

The TGA analysis for the samples in this project was performed twice: one run till before the decomposition started, considering that the aged sample does not undergo significant mass losses, and another run to 800°C to determine the steps. To make it compatible with the natural degradation mechanism, activation energies at different heat rates were found for the sample heated to 180°C.

Figure 2.14: Thermogravimetric Analysis

[46]

Table 2.3: TGA Specification

Manufacturer	Hitachi
Model	NEXTA STA300
Temperature range	RT to 1500°C
Heating rates	0.1°C to 100°C / min
Gas flow rates	50 to 500 ml/min
Gas type	N2, Air, Ar, O2

Finding Activation Energy

As per Coats and Redfern model^[47,48]

$$\ln\left(\frac{-\ln(1-\alpha)}{T^2}\right) = \ln\left[\frac{AR}{\beta E}\left(1 - 2\left(\frac{RT}{E}\right)\right)\right] - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (2.8)$$

where, β = Heating rate E_a = Activation energy R = Universal gas constant A = Pre-exponent factor T = Temperature at which the sample is treated

$$\alpha = \frac{w_i - w_t}{w_i - w_f} \quad (2.9)$$

The plot of $\ln\left(\frac{-\ln(1-\alpha)}{T^2}\right)$ vs $1/T$ gives a slope, which when multiplied by universal gas constant gives an activation energy, E_a .

2.5.2 DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY

It is a tool utilised to measure the heat that is either absorbed or released by the material which helps to determine the glass transition temperature, specific heat capacity, and crystallization^[46]. The one utilized in the project is Heat flux DSC which consists of the heat sink, heat resistor, heater and the sample and reference holder^[49].

Figure 2.15: Differential Scanning Calorimetry
[46]

Table 2.4: DSC Specification

Manufacturer	Hitachi
Model	DSC 7020
Temperature range	-150°C to 725°C
Heating rates	0.1°C to 100°C / min
Gas flow rates	50 to 500 ml/min
Gas type	N2, Air, Ar, O2

2.5.3 UNIVERSAL TESTING MACHINE

To determine the mechanical properties, Universal Testing Machine is used worldwide. Multiple tests such as tensile strength, compressions, and shear tests can be done in this machine making it versatile in application. There are several standards a user can follow. However, for this project purpose due to the availability of numerous literatures that make it easier for comparison, the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard is followed.

With aging, the binder properties deviate from the unaged sample affecting the performance parameters that are highly critical in any designed flight. One investigation on aged binders with different crosslinking agent showed that the sample tensile strength increased, but the elongation properties were unaffected^[50].

Figure 2.16: Universal Testing Machine

Table 2.5: UTM Specification

Manufacturer	Instron
Loading Capacity	5 kN
Weight	51 kg
Maximum Power	VA.
Software	Bluehill

2.5.4 DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

The dynamic mechanical analysis was performed in DMA 242 E Artemis model with make by Netzsch, where the cooling agents were Liquid Nitrogen and Air Intra Cooler. The test specimens were in planar rectangular form (5mm * 4mm * 5mm) and tested in the tension mode. The sample was subjected to a frequency of 1 Hz, an oscillation force of 0.5 N, and an amplitude of 10 μm . Storage modulus, loss modulus, and loss tangent were determined as a function of temperature ranging from -125°C to 100°C at a $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating rate for aged and unaged specimens.

Figure 2.17: DMA 242 E Artemis

2.6 CROSS-LINKING DENSITY

2.6.1 ESTIMATION FROM EQUILIBRIUM SWELLING METHOD

The cross-linking density was found using equilibrium swelling methods. Five cuts of aged and unaged samples with the specific dimension (18.6 mm * 8mm * 4.7 mm) were first measured for their initial mass ($m_0 = 0.59$ gm), which were then soaked in a bottle filled with 15 ml THF solvent for 5 days as in the literature^[51]. After reaching the equilibrium swelling, the samples taken out from the bottle were blotted using filter paper to ensure the removal of the surface THF. The swollen mass after equilibrium condition, m_1 was measured and found to be as presented in the table. Similarly, the dried mass (m_2) was measured after the swollen sample was kept in a hot air oven at 70 °C for 14 hours, until it reached a constant mass.

The cross-linking density was found using Flory-Rehner equation

$$C_d = -\frac{[\ln(1 - V_r) + V_r + \chi V_r^2]}{V_s(V_r^{1/3} - V_r/2)} \quad (2.10)$$

$$V_r = \frac{m_0/\rho_0}{m_0/\rho_0 + (m_1 - m_0)/\rho_c} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\chi = 0.487 + 0.228V_r \quad (2.12)$$

Where χ is Flory–Huggins interaction parameter, which tells how compatible the solvent is with the polymer. The lower the χ value, the better the interaction between the solvent and polymer. V_r is the polymer volume fraction, V_r is the molar volume of the solvent, ρ_0 is the initial density of the polymer and ρ_c is the THF density.

The swelling ratio and the sol fraction is determined using the equation as

$$\text{Swelling ratio, } Q = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_2} \quad (2.13)$$

$$\text{Sol fraction, } S_f = \frac{m_0 - m_2}{m_0} \times 100\% \quad (2.14)$$

2.6.2 ESTIMATION FROM STRESS-STRAIN CURVE

The stress strain curves are shown in the figure 3.13. The Young's modulus (E) is found from the initial slope of the stress-strain curve which is utilized to calculate the crosslink density using the relation as stated^[52].

$$E = 3C_{dE}RT \quad (2.15)$$

2.6.3 ESTIMATION FROM MOONEY-RIVLIN PLOTS

The Mooney-Rivlin equation is widely accepted to calculate degree of crosslinking. Based on phenomenological theory, the equation for various elastomers is found as^[52,53,54]:

$$\frac{\sigma}{\lambda - \lambda^{-2}} = C_1 + C_2\lambda^{-1} \quad (2.16)$$

Where, σ is the engineering stress that is proportional to the inverse of the original cross-sectional area and λ is the ratio of strained length to the original length at every step. The plot of $\frac{\sigma}{\lambda - \lambda^{-2}}$ vs. λ^{-1} till the linear elastic region of the stress-strain gives a straight line plot. The equation from Mooney-Rivlin plot gives an intercept and a slope from which crosslink density is calculated using the relation as

$$C_{dMR} = \frac{C_1}{RT} \quad (2.17)$$

2.6.4 ESTIMATION FROM STORAGE MODULUS

The value of storage modulus (E') is available with the dynamic mechanical analysis of the specimen at temperature range from -125°C to 100°C . Based on theory of rubber elasticity^[52],

$$C_{dSM} = \frac{E'}{6RT} \quad (2.18)$$

E' changes with temperature, thus, E' is considered for the room temperature (25°C) and the crosslink density is calculated using the equation 2.18.

Chapter 3

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS - ACTIVATION ENERGIES

3.1.1 ROOM TEMPERATURE TO 180°C

The activation energies in the presence of air are notably lower than the those observed on analysis done in the presence of nitrogen as shown in the table 3.1. This represents that the sample undergoes a reaction with oxygen in the environment facilitating the breakdown of chemical bonds. These reactions occur more readily in air, thereby, lowering the activation energy essential for reactions to occur. Thus, sample undergoes rapid degradation as represented by the lower activation energy.

Whereas, the inert environment does not promote the reaction, facilitating the energy barrier in the process. The oxidative degradation process is suppressed as a result of nitrogen which results in significantly lower chemical changes. Thus, the activation energies in nitrogen are substantially high in comparison. The selected operating temperature range inferred from the weight loss plot of TGA analysis to 180°C best fits the ageing mechanism as the mass variation is lower throughout the storage.

Figure 3.1: Plot of log function vs $1000/T$ for cured HTPB in presence of Air at different heat rates

Table 3.1: Activation energies (kJ/mol) in Air and N_2

Heating rates ($^{\circ}C/min$)	Ea (Air)	Ea (N_2)
5	65.29	157.99
7	81.59	101.11
10	64.69	73.72

Similarly, the activation energies for S2 and S3 in air were found to be 52.9 kJ/mol and 53.02 kJ/mol respectively. The variation in activation energy between these two samples is minimal; thus, S2 and S3 are considered for ageing studies together keeping the same thermal cycle in the incubator.

3.1.2 ROOM TEMPERATURE TO 800°C

The mass variation with temperature in nitrogen is obtained using TGDTA as shown in the figure 3.2. It is observed that the decomposition of all three compositions completed in two steps. The initial decomposition is due to the cleavage of the urethane linkage while the second step decomposition is due to crosslinking and depolymerization of HTPB

bonds.

The major mass loss for S1 initiated at around 230°C with residue less than 2% at 490°C for 5°C/min heating rate. Decomposition started at 220°C for S2 with complete decomposition at around 485°C. Similarly, for S3, decomposition began at 230°C with complete consumption at around 485°C. Looking at the three TGA analysis profile, it is clear that the degradation is abrupt at the second stage representing breakdown of HTPB chain structure.

Figure 3.2: Weight % vs. temperature profiles of S1, S2, and S3 at various heating rates obtained from TGA in Nitrogen

The thermal stability and the blends degradation were studied through thermogravimetric analysis conducted under both air and nitrogen atmospheres. The variation in the decomposition mechanisms was clearly reflected in the TGA curves. In air, there were three thermal decomposition stages in both S2 and S3, whereas, only two degradation stages were evident in an inert environment. When the weight % reached 95%, the temperature corresponding to that point was considered to be the initial degradation temperature (T_{de}) as stated elsewhere^[55]. The maximum weight loss rate was also observed at a particular temperature (T_{max}) that was found using DTG curve which is presented in the table. Additionally, the residual char percentage at 600°C was determined from

the TGA data. The initial degradation step for both the sample occurred within the temperature range of 210°C–400°C, irrespective of the atmosphere. This initial degradation is primarily due to the breaking of urethane linkages. For the second degradation step, S2 decomposed in between 400°C–450°C in air and 400°C–480°C in nitrogen. The sample S3 had second degradation in the range of 400°C–459°C in air and 400°C–485°C in nitrogen . The third degradation stage was observed only in the sample tested under air condition. For sample S2, the degradation happened in between 450°C–564°C, while for sample S3, it was in between 480°C–552°C.

The third degradation stage observed in this thermal oxidative degradation in air relates to the breakdown of carbonaceous char. It involves carbon char reaction with atmospheric oxygen at elevated temperatures, forming other gaseous products and reducing the weight. In contrast, under nitrogen condition, the decomposition occurred in two stages in absence of oxidative reactions, thereby yielding higher amount of residual char as compared to those under air condition as shown in the table 3.2.

Figure 3.3: TGA and DTG curves for S2 in both N_2 and air at 5°C/min

Figure 3.4: TGA and DTG curves for S3 in both N_2 and air at 5°C/min

Table 3.2: TGA data of S2 and S3 in nitrogen and air atmosphere

Sample Code	T_{de} (°C)		T_{s1} (°C)		T_{max} (°C)		T_{s3} (°C)		Char wt.% at 600°C	
	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂	Air	N ₂
S2	228.7	217.9	241.4	326.9	437.5	448.6	511.7	-	0.8	2.59
S3	235.9	239.5	251.3	328.08	438.2	449.5	507.1	-	0	1.6

The activation energies for both grades of HPTB in both decomposition stages is found using Coats and Redfern model plotting the log function versus inverse of temperature. The activation energy for the first step is in the range of 63–67 kJ/mol and the second step is between 170–180 kJ/mol for two HTPB grades available in the laboratory.

Figure 3.5: Plot of log function vs 1000/T for cured HTPB_A in presence of Nitrogen at 10°C/min

Figure 3.6: Plot of log function vs 1000/T for cured HTPB_B in presence of Nitrogen at 10°C/min

Figure 3.7: Comparison plot for $HTPBm_A$ and $HTPBm_B$

Table 3.3: Activation Energies in stages for different cured HTPB

Stage	HTPBm_A (kJ/mol)	HTPBm_B (kJ/mol)	Ea literature ^[48] (kJ/mol)
1	63.84	67.01	78.66
2	171.6	179.89	190.79

3.2 MEAN ACCELERATED TEMPERATURE PROFILE

The mean temperature profile for all the seasons was smoothed using spline interpolation in OriginLab represented in figure 3.8. These profile were obtained following the iterative calculation of accelerated time where LHS and RHS of Arrhenius equation 2.1 are required to be equal. With the optimized τ_a , all the variables in equation 2.3 are known and thus, accelerated temperature at specific times for a mean temperature of a day till the end of a season are found. For comparison of accounting season-wise accelerated time with year-wise calculation, the accelerated days required to simulate a year is found to be 64 days, 13 days more than what could have been when accounted for season-wise studies. Likewise, for S2 and S3, accelerated time is reduced to 72 days, saving 17 days of extra time required when considering year-based calculation.

Figure 3.8: Comparison plot for natural and accelerated temperature profile corresponding to each season

While the winter cycle for a day was supposed to have accelerated time of 1.9 hours, the actual time to run the program took around 2.1 hours as demonstrated in the fig. 3.9a. This is because extra time for each cycle was given 3 minutes 40 seconds divided into 8 segments to turn on the compressor. Doing so, it reduced the temperature in chamber from exceeding 65°C keeping operation within the limit. This also assisted to avoid temperature surge and minimize the differences in actual temperature's value from the set-point value. Thus, similar method was applied for other two seasons to avoid variation.

Table 3.4: Actual cycle execution time and compressor-based control strategy across seasonal temperature cycles

Parameters	Winter	Summer	Monsoon
No. of cycles	121	122	123
Compressor time for each cycle, min	3.66	3.5	3
Total extra time required, hrs	29.04	10.91	5.46

(a) Winter

(b) Summer

(c) Monsoon

Figure 3.9: Actual plot for accelerated temperature profile corresponding to each season

Table 3.5: Accelerated time parameters for S1

Season	ΔT_m (°C)	Calculated τ_a (hrs)	Actual τ_a (hrs)	Total Days
Winter	31	1.9	2.1	10
Summer	22	4.4	4.6	22
Monsoon	24	3.7	3.8	19
Yearly	22	4.2	—	64

Note: τ_a refers to the accelerated ageing time per natural day. Compressor ON time was factored in the actual run duration including ramp condition.

(a) Unaged Specimens

(b) Aged Specimens

Figure 3.10: Aged and Unaged Specimens

Similarly, the accelerated temperature profile is found for HTPB-blends having the viscosity as illustrated in the picture below.

Figure 3.11: Shear-dependent viscosity of HTPB blends at room temperature

The reduction in viscosity by certain degree increases the miscibility of the blends, a highly preferred features in making a propellant. The composition with epoxy LY 556 demonstrated lower viscosity as compared to the HTPB alone, making it a desirable property for the further studies.

The accelerated parameters for the blends are

Table 3.6: Accelerated time for S2 and S3

Season	ΔT_m ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Calculated τ_a per day(hrs)	Calculated total days
Winter	31	3.04	15
Summer	22	6	30
Monsoon	24	5.24	27
Yearly	22	5.83	89

3.3 HEAT TRANSFER ACROSS A HTPB SLAB

The time required for the centre of slab to reach the temperature as on surface was under 6 minutes. Each season has 8 temperature segments having varying total run times. Run time for each segment in winter is 14 minutes, 33 minutes for summer, and 28 minutes for monsoon . This duration allows sufficient time to reach thermal equilibrium at the center of the slab. The corresponding temperature distributions for each season are shown in the figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Time–temperature relation across the slab at all seasons

3.4 UNIVERSAL TESTING MACHINE - MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical behaviour of the binder demonstrated significant changes in the properties as a result of thermal ageing. As shown in the table 3.7, the load specimen sustained increased from 5.9 N to 8.4 N. As the specimens were aged for a natural period of 1 year, the substantial increase in initial modulus is observed, increasing by around 110% for the displacement rate of 50 mm/min. This is due to oxidative reduction of binder in presence of atmospheric air that has encouraged crosslinking^[52,56]. Conversely, reduction in

elongation percentage by around 40 % was observed suggesting that the material became more stiff due to the impact of atmospheric and thermal degradation.

Figure 3.13: Stress vs Strain curve for aged and unaged HTPB

Table 3.7: Effect of Ageing on the mechanical properties of binder

Condition	Max. load (N)	% Elongation	Modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Unaged	5.9	339.02	0.15	0.24
Aged	8.4	204.9	0.32	0.36
% Changes	+42.37	-39.5	+110.07	+46.69

3.5 CROSS-LINKING DENSITY

The storage modulus at room temperature for the unaged and aged specimen are 0.54 MPa and 0.93 MPa respectively. Thus, from the calculation as in the equation 2.18, the crosslink density is as presented in the table. The crosslink density values using other methods stated in the experimental methodology are also represented in the same table. The crosslink density for the aged samples found using storage modulus and Flory-Rehner equation almost doubled than that of unaged sample. Charlesby-Pinner equation

(a) Aged S1 samples immersed in THF for swelling study

(b) Aged S1 specimens after solvent immersion and oven drying

Figure 3.14: Five aged S1 samples for Equilibrium Swelling Test

Table 3.8: Parameters found using Equilibrium Swelling Method

Conditions	m_1 (mg)	m_2 (mg)	Swelling ratio	<i>Solfraction</i> (S)
Unaged	3.51	0.39	7.94	0.23
Aged	3.14	0.48	5.59	0.19

(a) Unaged

(b) Aged

Figure 3.15: Plot of $\frac{\sigma}{\lambda - \lambda^2}$ vs λ^{-1} from the Mooney–Rivlin equation

Plotting the LHS of Mooney–Rivlin equation against the inverse of the extension ratio (λ) gave the range for straight line. The intercept obtained is C_1 and the slope is C_2 .

One of the key observation that is needed to highlight in this swelling study is about the irregular structural transformation of the sample upon removal from the solvent after 5 days of immersion. This phenomena inducing morphological changes such as curling and surface rupturing is likely due to THF solvent trapped within the planar rectangular specimen geometry. The solvent evaporation induced surface deformation

Table 3.9: Crosslink Density using various methods for unaged and aged samples

Parameters	C_d	C_{dE}	C_{dMR}	C_{dSM}	C_{dCP}
	(mol/m ³)				
Unaged	21.15	20.17	24.38	36.31	lower
Aged	47.9	43.03	55.38	62.53	greater

was spontaneous while it was kept for measuring the weight, the study of which may bring whole new chapter of study about the solvent evaporation dynamics.

Figure 3.16: Surface deformation in aged sample taken out from THF after swelling

3.6 DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

The DMA measurements were employed to determine storage modulus, loss modulus, and loss tangent as a function of temperature from -125°C to 100°C. The storage modulus and loss modulus both were found higher for aged specimen. This is attributed to the increased crosslink density of the aged sample that had reduced chain mobility and increased stiffness. This indicated that the aged one require higher force to achieve a small strain during dynamic loading. As seen in fig. 3.17a, in glassy region, the storage modulus for aged sample is significantly higher than that of unaged sample representing the changes in chain structure of the sample due to crosslinking. Even in the transition region, the aged sample maintained a higher curve for storage modulus, indicating good elastic energy storage.

Similarly, the higher loss modulus for aged sample as in the fig. 3.17b is associated with the increased chain interactions in constrained manner. The sharp and narrower $\tan \delta$ peak implied that the damping effect for the aged sample is reduced. This came in agreement with the study conducted to find crosslink density. The glass transition temperature for the aged sample was high. This was due to crosslinking reaction that made material compact and stiff^[57].

Figure 3.17: Comparison of DMA properties for aged and unaged samples

Table 3.10: Properties from DMA

Parameters	Unaged	Aged
T_g , °C	-70.7	-67.4
E' at T_g , MPa	30.75	69.11
E' at 25°C, MPa	0.54	0.93
Loss tangent at peak	1.13	1.37

Chapter 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND FUTURE SCOPES

4.1 SUMMARY

A cyclic accelerated thermal ageing method was developed by following the procedures outlined in the literature to investigate the impact of thermal fluctuations on both the mechanical and chemical properties of HTPB binders. Thermal fluctuation is one of the major factors causing significant degradation in binder properties when exposed to air. However, many research studies have been conducted under isothermal conditions, which does not replicate natural temperature cycles. Therefore, addressing this research gap, accounting for the diurnal and seasonal ambient temperature variation, the thermal cycles for accelerated aging simulating a particular geographic location were developed for binders following the sinusoidal temperature distribution equation.

15 T-type thermocouples were employed to evaluate the temperature distribution across the vertical section and walls of the chamber within a thermal incubator. Accelerated ageing of HTPB binder was performed over a laboratory timescale of 51 days which is equivalent to one-year natural exposure time cycle. Activation energies were determined using the Coats and Redfern model. The effects of accelerated thermal ageing of binder under atmospheric conditions were characterized through variations in crosslink density, changes in tensile properties and dynamic mechanical properties. Finally, a potential binder composition was investigated and accelerated time for these formulation were determined for further future research study.

4.2 CONCLUSIONS

In the literature, it is prevalent that the performance and stability of the solid motor are affected by changes in mechanical and chemical properties due to ageing. This brings undesirable performance that lead to catastrophic failure. To understand the nature of changes that propellants undergo throughout storage, natural ageing and accelerated age-

ing are most widely used. Both isothermal and cyclic ageing methodologies avail insights into mechanical and chemical properties defining the dynamic and static relation that exists from the molecular level to the whole structural level, building inter-dependencies of chemical and mechanical properties together.

Oxidative linking of binders and oxidizers with time causes reduced mechanical properties that are perilous to operate. Besides, the desired properties may not be achieved at the time of operation due to factors such as creep, fatigue, and thermal as well as static and dynamic loads. Therefore, the HTPB binder is tested for crosslink density, storage modulus, elongation and tensile strength which is compared with the aged HTPB binder specimen properties post-determination of accelerated time. The storage modulus and loss modulus for the aged specimen is found above the curve of unaged specimen. A similar study has to be conducted for the propellant composition so that the correlation between binder ageing and propellant ageing can be developed. Similarly, performing thermogravimetric analysis of unaged cured HTPB in both air and nitrogen confirmed variation in activation energies. The presence of binders in propellant undergoes reactions during storage due to a favorable environment, reducing the activation energy and promoting crosslinking.

As the natural degradation is dominant up to 65°C, the change in mean temperature was selected to avoid crossing the limitation posed by the actual deterioration. Heat transfer across the half depth of the binder slab was studied and found sufficient time for homogeneous distribution in performing accelerated studies. Furthermore, the seasonal temperature amplitude was utilized to account for both the diurnal and seasonal temperature variation mimicking real-world environmental conditions. The viscoelastic behaviour of the binder was observed in the stress-strain curve. So, on performing the dynamic mechanical analysis, the storage modulus at room temperature for unaged and aged sample were found to be 0.54 and 0.93 MPa respectively. The increase in modulus by twice of the unaged specimen is strongly supported by the crosslink density tests. The crosslink density for the aged sample using equilibrium swelling method is more than double of unaged sample. This indicates that the binder had undergone heavy oxidation reaction causing reduced chain mobility and deterioration. Thus, elongation property of the specimen is reduced as a result of reduced chain mobility and increased crosslink density.

4.3 FUTURE SCOPES

While the study successfully demonstrated the process involved in finding cyclic accelerated ageing methodologies, certain problems were encountered while performing Universal Tensile Testing of cured HTPB samples. The future research direction could be in formulating particular standards to meet the requirement for tensile testing of elastomers.

Subsequently, results obtained from the developed cyclic accelerated ageing method can be compared with those from natural ageing studies and fine-tune the parameters for greater accuracy. Upon performing thermogravimetric analysis and determining activation energies, the propellant samples can be subjected to ageing under simulated environmental conditions of the selected geographical location. Thereafter, the samples can be subjected to mechanical testing and derive the relation for safe storage limit. The burn rate variation can also be studied post ageing of propellant. The HTPB blends with epoxies can be utilized to formulate a propellant and study performance characteristics. Thus, post successful research study, the composition could offer great advantage in practical application, thereby increasing shelf-life of the propellants.

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